

Out-of-autoclave manufacturing of thermoset composites using frontal polymerization: An overview

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Motivation: Faster, Cleaner Composite Manufacturing

Kim et al. *Composites Part A*, 2019

Conventional autoclave-based manufacturing of thermoset composites

- Is complex, expensive, and slow
- Requires a lot of energy
- Involves large capital investments

Autoclave for curing large composite structures for Boeing 777

Heated mold for wind turbine blades

Objectives:

- To reduce **time to cure** of thermoset composites by (at least) **two orders of magnitude**
- To reduce **energy consumption** by (at least) **six orders of magnitude**
- To **substantially** reduce **capital investment costs** and **CO₂ emission**

Frontal Polymerization (FP)

Exothermic reaction with self-propagating polymerization front

Applications to manufacturing

- **Rapid, low-energy manufacturing of thermoset polymers and composites**
- Additive manufacturing of freeform structures
- Growth-printing manufacturing

FP and Composite Manufacturing: Recent Interest

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Frontal Polymerization for the Rapid Obtainment of Polymer Composites

Giulio Malucelli*, and Alberto Mariani*

ADVANCED SCIENCE

Research Article |

Efficient Exothermic Press toward Ultrafast and Scalable Manufacturing of Complex Polymer Composites

Amirreza Tarafdar, Haining Zhang, Xinlu Wang, Andrea J. Hoe, Kaiyue Deng, Kelvin Fu, Quinn Qiao, Ian D. Hosein, Yeqing Wang

First published: 17 July 2025 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202509336>

Review on Frontal Polymerization Behavior for Thermosetting Resins: Materials, Modeling and Application

by Tingting Luo

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Polymers 2024, 16(2), 185; <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16020185>

Cite Sh

Article | [Open access](#) | Published: 20 May 2025

Additive manufacturing of carbon fiber-reinforced thermoset composites via in-situ thermal curing

Carter F. Dojan, Morteza Ziaee, Alireza Masoumipour, Samuel J. Radosevich & Mostafa Yourdkhani

Nature Communications 16, Article number: 4691 (2025) | [Cite this article](#)

Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing

Volume 192, May 2025, 108779

A review on energy-efficient manufacturing for high-performance fibre-reinforced composites

Yushen Wang ^a, Thomas D.S. Thorn ^a, Yi Liu ^b, Suresh G. Advani ^c, Dimitrios G. Papageorgiou ^a, Emiliano Bilotti ^d, Han Zhang ^{a e}

Thermo-Chemical Modeling of FP

Rate of change of internal energy Heat diffusion Heat released by FROMP

$$\text{Heat equation} \quad \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 T + \rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t}$$

$$\text{Cure kinetics} \quad \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha)$$

$t = 0.00$ s

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Cure kinetics parameters:
A E g(α)

t = 0.00 s

Front speed estimate

$$v_f^2 = \max_{\varepsilon} \frac{A\kappa}{\rho H_r} \frac{\bar{R}\tilde{T}(\varepsilon)^2}{E} \exp\left(-\frac{E}{\bar{R}\tilde{T}(\varepsilon)}\right) \frac{1}{\Pi(\varepsilon)}$$

(Kumar *et al.*,
J Polym. Sci.,
2021)

FP Manufacturing of Composites: VARTM

Reinforcement: 12 plies of Toray T300 2x2 Twill carbon fabric
(3K tow size, areal weight=204 g/m²)

$V_{\text{void}} = 0.18\%$, $V_f \sim 51\%$

(Robertson *et al.*, *Nature*, 2018)

Modeling FP in Composites: Homogenized Reaction-Diffusion Model

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + (1 - \phi) \rho_r H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \overline{\rho C_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A_r \exp\left(-\frac{E_r}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

where (for unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite)

$$\begin{cases} \overline{\rho C_p} = \rho_r C_{p,r} (1 - \phi) + \rho_f C_{p,f} \phi \\ \bar{\kappa} = \kappa_r (1 - \phi) + \kappa_f \phi \end{cases}$$

DCPD

Carbon Fibers

$\kappa_r = 0.152 \frac{W}{m.K}$	$\kappa_f = 9.363 \frac{W}{m.K}$
$\rho_r = 980 \frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\rho_f = 1800 \frac{kg}{m^3}$
$C_{p,r} = 1600 \frac{J}{kg.K}$	$C_{p,f} = 753.6 \frac{J}{kg.K}$

(Goli et al., Composite A, 2020)

Front Speed vs. Fiber Volume Fraction ϕ

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + (1 - \phi) \rho_r H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \overline{\rho C_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A_r \exp\left(-\frac{E_r}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

$$\tilde{V}_f = \max_{\varepsilon} \sqrt{\frac{A_r \bar{\kappa}}{(1 - \phi) \rho_r H_r} \frac{RT(\varepsilon)^2}{E_r} \exp\left(\frac{-E_r}{RT(\varepsilon)}\right) \frac{1}{\Pi[m, n, C, \alpha_c, \alpha_0, \varepsilon]}}$$

(Kumar et al., J. Polymer Science, 2021)

(Vyas et al., Composite Sc. & Techn., 2019)

Validation: Unidirectional Carbon-DCPD Composite

Through-Thickness FP Curing

IR video of experiment

Curing of 10 cm × 20 cm panel

*Infusion: 90 sec Trigger: 15 sec (4800 J) Volume Fraction: 65%
Void Content: 0.03% T_g : 118 °C*

1D FE Model: Validation

Experimental trigger

Model validation

Flux vs. time trigger

Panel area: 0.012 m^2

Exp. energy expenditure = $12,230 \text{ J}$

Objective: Minimize applied heat flux vs. time while achieving same quality of composite ($\alpha_{min} > \alpha_{crit}$)

Method: gradient-based optimization using analytical sensitivity analysis of objective function and constraints

Gradient-Based Optimization Results

Optimal trigger profile uses 27% less energy than reference experimental trigger

Thermomechanical response of panel fabricated using optimal trigger is equivalent to the reference panel

FP-based Composite Extrusion Manufacturing

Rapid Out-of-oven Lamination

High-throughput lamination for rapid curing of composite beams and panels

Abdullah *et al.*, *Composites A*, 2025

Reactive Extrusion of Woven Composite Tubes

Self-sustaining front propagates longitudinally through extruded tube

Kim *et al.*, *In preparation*

Mesoscale Modeling of FP in Laminate and Woven Composites

Objectives

1. Develop analytical and computational models to capture the impact of reinforcement properties and geometry on the meso- and macro-scale propagation of the front

- Composite laminates
- Woven composites

2. Optimize the manufacturing process

- Reduce time or energy consumption while maintaining composite quality

FP of Short-Fiber Composites

$$\beta = 15^\circ \quad \phi = 0.1$$

Time: 0.00

Thermal properties and cure kinetics parameters of DCPD resin [19].

$\kappa_r \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}} \right)$	$\rho_r \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right)$	$C_{pr} \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}} \right)$	$E \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	$A \left(\frac{1}{\text{s}} \right)$	n	m	C	α_c	$H_r \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{g}} \right)$
0.15	980	1600	110.75	8.55×10^{15}	1.72	0.77	14.48	0.41	350

Physical properties of short carbon fiber [23].

$\kappa_{f1} \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}} \right)$	$\kappa_{f2} \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}} \right)$	$C_{pf} \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}} \right)$	$\rho_f \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right)$	$\frac{l_f}{d}$
9.3	0.67	753.6	1800	100

$$\beta = 15^\circ \quad \phi = 0.4$$

Front Inclination γ

Thermal conductivities: Halpin–Tsai model (Choy *et al.*, 1994; Progelhof *et al.*, 1976; Nielsen, 1974; Agari *et al.*, 1991)

In material frame

$$\mu_1 = \frac{\kappa_{f1}/\kappa_m - 1}{\kappa_{f1}/\kappa_m + 2l_f/d}$$

$$\mu_2 = \frac{\kappa_{f2}/\kappa_m - 1}{\kappa_{f2}/\kappa_m + 2}$$

$$\kappa_{//} = \frac{1 + (l_f/d)\mu_1\phi}{1 - \mu_1\phi} \kappa_m$$

$$\kappa_{\perp} = \frac{1 + 2\mu_2\phi}{1 - \mu_2\phi} \kappa_m$$

Front inclination angle

$$\gamma = \tan^{-1} \frac{\overline{\kappa}_{12}}{\overline{\kappa}_{22}}$$

In global frame

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \overline{\kappa}_{11} & \overline{\kappa}_{12} \\ \overline{\kappa}_{21} & \overline{\kappa}_{22} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos^2\beta \overline{\kappa}_{//} + \sin^2\beta \overline{\kappa}_{\perp} & \cos\beta\sin\beta(\overline{\kappa}_{//} - \overline{\kappa}_{\perp}) \\ \cos\beta\sin\beta(\overline{\kappa}_{//} - \overline{\kappa}_{\perp}) & \sin^2\beta \overline{\kappa}_{//} + \cos^2\beta \overline{\kappa}_{\perp} \end{Bmatrix}$$

Front Velocity V_f

$$v_f(\beta) = \sqrt{\frac{(v_{f\parallel} v_{f\perp})^2 (1 + \tan^2 \beta)}{v_{f\parallel}^2 \tan^2 \beta + v_{f\perp}^2}}$$

(Topkaya et al., ACS Applied Polymer Materials, 2022)

Conclusions

- Frontal polymerization (FP) provides an attractive faster, lower-energy, lower-CO₂, out-of-autoclave alternative for the manufacturing of composite panels and tubes
- The propagation of the polymerization front can be captured using a coupled (homogenized) reaction-diffusion thermo-chemical model in terms of the temperature and degree-of-cure fields
- An analytical expression of the dependence of the front speed on chemical and thermal parameters has been derived
- Manufacturing process can be optimized by combining homogenized finite element model with analytical sensitivity analysis

Current Activities Related to FP-Based Manufacturing

- **Mechanism-based modeling** of cure kinetics and FP-induced patterning (DOE EFRC)
- Discovering **recyclable FP-compatible thermoset** polymers and composites through high-throughput experiments and machine learning (DOE EFRC)
- FP-based **3D printing/extrusion** of polymers and composites (AFOSR and NSF)
- FP-based manufacturing of **large space-based composite structures** (DARPA)

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Thank you!

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